

Climate
Compatible
Growth

KENYA

The Kenya CCG Network presents

Whole Energy System Green Hydrogen Workshop

February 23rd
Maanzoni Lodge, Kenya

Friday, February 23rd

EAT

- 09:30 – 09:45 Workshop opening and round of introduction
- 09:45 – 10:15 **Introduction** to the Green Hydrogen National strategy (20 min presentation + 10 min Q&A) Eng Kihara Mungai (EPRA)
- 10:15 – 10:45 **Presentation 1:** CCG activities on hydrogen (20 min presentation + 10 min Q&A) Dr Alycia Leonard (CCG – Oxford University)
- 10:45 – 11:15 **Presentation 2:** CCG Whole Energy System Model overview (20 min presentation + 10 min Q&A) Dr Pietro Lubello (CCG – UCL)
- 11:15 – 11:45 Break - refreshments
- 11:45 – 12:15 **Presentation 3:** CCG – Green Hydrogen implementation in the WESM (20 min presentation + 10 min Q&A) Mr Joshua Oduor (GIZ)
- 12:15 – 13:15 **Interactive Session 1:** Revision of model implementation and scenarios
- 13:15 – 14:15 **Lunch**
- 14:15 – 15:15 **Interactive Session 2:** Open discussion – Collection of feedbacks on implementation and scenarios
- 15:15 – 15.30 Closing and future work

